

A trophoblast immunity program.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

East Islip, NY USA 11730

Thy1 and PDCD4 were silenced concomitant with FLRT3 and IFI16 activation during TE commitment in the human embryo, alluding to programmed changes in immune receptors that operate together in a system that functions like pruning of the synapses for fine tuning of neuronal architecture. Igsf receptors were actively expressed early in human development in utero; this included signature changes in expression of Igsf8 and Igsf21. HLA and HCG expression guided immune activation status in utero during TE commitment: this included HLA-DRB family class II receptor and HCG15, but MHC genes were otherwise not perturbed during TE lineage commitment.

Citations

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